

IFC-Based Schedule Optimization

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Abstract

A construction or demolition scheduling problem with resource allocation has both the challenge of sequencing the correct order of works to the elements being constructed or demolished, and assigning the correct labour teams to do this work. Solving this problem requires the knowledge of a wide array of factors, from sequence to coordination of trades, to safety and skill. Even though scheduling and resource allocation problems have been studied at length in the past century, the current existence of modern technologies, i.e. Building Information Modelling and Evolutionary Algorithms, promises the potential to create new ways of solving these problems.

This study explores literature on the confluence of these two technologies in the specific context of schedule optimization, and then proposes a method of performing schedule and resource optimization for construction and demolition, based on IFC models and their elements' GUIDs. With the use of a precedence matrix and a chromosome repair strategy, an evolutionary algorithm, NSGA-II is used to generate multiple results bearing optimal schedule orders, and construction and deconstruction costs and times. The methodology is then tested on two case studies, where its efficacy is proven on a demolition problem and a simplified construction problem.

The findings of the study show the potential for use of the proposed schedule optimization system within construction and demolition, and proposals are made on methods and strategies to build upon and extend this work.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/1WZF0vIOTIM>

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